

PHONETIC AND STYLISTIC CATEGORIES

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PhD in Philology, lecturer (Baku, Azerbaijan)***Abstract**

Stylistic phonetics refers to the use of the phonetic capabilities of a language for stylistic purposes. It is known that the task of phonetics is to study the sound structure, sound composition and sound laws of language. The beauty of any word and expression is connected not only with its meaning, but also with the harmony of sounds in it, their correspondence to the meaning. The stylistic role of phonetic means depends on their position in the text; it is any sound, word, expression that acquires a stylistic connotation and beauty within the sentence and text. On the other hand, the local use of phonetic means contributes to the self-expression of other means of language. Since phonetic stylistics covers a number of sections of linguistics, its study is important from the point of view of the full disclosure of these relationships, the definition of patterns of literary language, the essence of its norms and even boundaries. On the other hand, the study of this topic is also relevant from the point of view of studying the relationship of languages with different systems. Thus, the reasons for the formation and formation of phonetic stylistics are not specific to one language, but are universal in nature. Historically, phonetic and stylistic means of expression were common to almost all languages of the world and over time occupied a unique place in the written monuments and folklore of each language.

The article defines phonetic and stylistic categories, which include emotionality and expressivity, alliteration, modality, repetition, symmetry and paronymy of different levels. Phonetic and stylistic categories are also closely related to textual categories. The interaction of language categories is associated with the integration of different levels of language.

Keywords: stylistic category, expressivity, emotionality, stylistics.

The degree of development of the problem. There are views of such linguists as R.G. Piotrovsky, M.N. Kozhina, Tosovich B., Courtenay B.I.A., Brandes M.P. on this topic, and these views are touched upon in the article.

The purpose of this article is to review existing ideas and considerations in linguistics related to phonetic and stylistic categories, to identify the role of individual components and functions of phonetic and stylistic categories and their analysis.

The methods and techniques of theoretical linguistics, including observation, description, structural analysis, situational-contextual and discursive analysis, were used in writing the study.

Each science has its own categories. As a universal fact, a linguistic phenomenon created by generalizing similar phenomena in all areas of language is called a category. In general, the category as a philosophical concept has a very broad content and includes generalized particular aspects of each science. In linguistics, it is also used in different fields with different meanings. Although linguistic categories related to various fields of linguistics have been studied in detail, especially the basic concepts and categories of stylistics, such as style, stylistic meaning, stylistic flavor, stylistic means, extralinguistic stylistic factors, etc., topical issues have not yet been fully resolved. Even in a number of linguistic dictionaries, including O.O. Akhmanova's dictionary, grammatical, morphological, lexico-semantic, and syntactic categories are distinguished, but phonetic stylistic categories are not mentioned.

R.G. Piotrovsky was the first to provide information about stylistic categories in linguistics, or rather, he gave their definitions. The author identifies "stylistic flavor", "additional stylistic shade" and

"emotional and evaluative value" as stylistic categories [1, p. 68].

M.N. Kozhina, interpreting the basic concepts and categories of stylistics, notes that style, stylistic meaning, stylistic coloring, stylistic means, extralinguistic stylistic factors, etc. remain relevant, although they do not have a complete definition, but analyzes imagery, emotionality and expressivity as categories of stylistics [2, pp. 13-23].

Stylistics experts note that stylistics as an independent field of linguistics also has its own categories. However, the definition of stylistic categories, manifested in the unity of a set of linguistic facts, is controversial; expressivity and emotionality are often used together, interpreted as synonymous concepts. They add expressiveness to speech and act as the main means of expression. Expressiveness as a universal category refers to a number of scientific and artistic disciplines: stylistics, linguistics, literary studies, art, aesthetics, logic, psychology, genetics, and includes homogeneous and heterogeneous relationships of formal, semantic, functional, and categorical units. This category expresses the logical, purposeful, subjective, emotional and aesthetic attitude of the speaker towards the interlocutor or object, has the property of influence, is enhanced, actualized and fixed in the communication process.

There is expressiveness of each level in the language: graphic, phonetic-phonological, lexical, phraseological, word-formation, grammatical and textual, and each of them is a form of subjective, emotional or aesthetic attitude and is realized by appropriate means [3, p. 6].

Theoretical issues of phonetic stylistics.

Style as a concept originated in ancient Greece, and then was studied at various levels in world linguistics. Initially, it was understood as the science of “beauty of language”, “individual style of a writer”, “manner of communication”, “beautiful speech”, “fluency, accuracy”, “literary expressiveness”. Stylistics as a science is a theory of styles that studies the inner side of the expression of thought in a word. From this point of view, stylistics realizes itself at the junction of literature and language. Even researchers divide stylistics into two parts: linguistic stylistics and literary stylistics. Although these are two aspects of the same problem, it is necessary to separate them [4, p. 10]. In the scientific literature, stylistics is considered in two different aspects: in the first case – as a way of using linguistic means, in the second – as a figurative and emotional expression of thought in individual artistic creation. It is impossible to completely separate them from each other, since they both relate to linguistic material. In general, “stylistics is a branch of linguistics that studies the laws of language used in specific communicative speech situations to subjectively influence people” [5, p. 17] It should be noted that to form images and emotional-expressive attitudes in a literary text, not only non-normative forms of expression or poetic expressions are used, but also normative linguistic forms, but even then they are subordinated to a specific purpose. Stylistics studies these issues comprehensively. Considering stylistics in a broader sense, V. Vinogradov identifies three main areas of research: 1) language style, which is a “system of systems” or structural style (colloquial, scientific, business, journalistic, official-clerical, etc.); 2) stylistics of speech, which studies the peculiarities of various semantic and expressive genres of oral and written speech; 3) stylistics of fiction – artistic stylistics that studies the style of all elements of a literary work, the individual style of the writer [6, p. 5]

The figurative and emotional expression of thought is given not only at the lexical and grammatical, but also at the phonetic level. At the same time, the potential possibilities of phonetic units, situational forms of manifestation are combined with normative forms, which is the field of study of phonetic stylistics. O.S. Akhmanova defines phonetic stylistics as follows: “Phonetic stylistics is a section of stylistics that studies the expressive features of pronounceable variants of words and phrases” [7, pp. 456-457]

The first use of the term “phonetic stylistics” in linguistics is associated with the name of N.S. Trubetskoy. In his book *Fundamentals of Phonology*, published in 1939, he identified phonetic stylistics as a special field of science [8, p. 9]. However, there were different opinions about the name of this linguistic area. It should be noted that “pronunciation style” is a term defined by the internal division of the phonetic style. However, sometimes “pronunciation styles” are used in a broader sense, that is, instead of “speech styles”.

A number of linguists use the term “pronunciation style” in the context of phonetic stylistics. I.A. Veshikova, speaking about “pronunciation style”, notes that three stages can be distinguished in its study: 1) the concept of “pronouncing style” in the works of L.V. Shcherba; 2) the stylistic concept of R.I. Avanesov; 3)

Phonostylistic issues in the works of M.V. Panov [9, p. 105]. Note that the author of the initial stage of studying phonostylistics, L.V. Shcherba, also called this concept the term “pronunciation style” [10, p. 21-25].

Types of phonetic and stylistic categories.

Since the phonetic layer of a language is determined in relation to other areas, these connecting categories are phonetic and stylistic categories. These include the categories of emotionality and expressivity, alliteration, modality, repetition and symmetry, as well as the category of paronymy from text categories.

The phonetics of language is emotional in itself, since any sound is an expression of a certain emotional state and meets with a corresponding emotional reaction. Since the style of expression in other layers is directly related to the phonetic style of expression, it is important to identify, reveal and explain the role of grammatical-morphological, grammatical-semantic categories in the emergence of emotional and expressive shades of meaning in the course of phonetic-stylistic research. In particular, intonation acts as a universal category. Expressiveness is manifested, in particular, in intonations expressing various meanings. It is obvious that the category of poetics originally appeared in linguistic theory, and the possibilities of using linguistic material in the expression of poetic thought were investigated. Some linguists consider poetic speech to be an aesthetic and poetic category [6, p.207].

In this sense, poetic language is a figurative language. It should be remembered that the sphere of expressivity, emotionality, and finally, poetics is the field of speech, and a specific poetic form does not exist abstractly in the form of paradigms and invariants of language.

One of the phonetic and stylistic categories is repetition. Repetition is inherent in all layers of language: from the phonetic level to syntax, to all linguistic units. Therefore, linguistics has shown that repetition is systemic in nature as a universal linguistic phenomenon. In linguistics, it has been shown that repetitions have a subjective modal meaning and perform three main functions: 1) Repetition is included in dialogical speech as a means of replica; 2) Is a means of enhancing expressiveness; 3) Is a means of expressing modality. We can note that modality manifests itself mainly in two aspects: objective and subjective. It is the meaning of subjective modality that is the object of the study of repetition. The functionalization of the repetition category is usually possible in the text. According to the forms of implementation, repetitions can be phonetic, morphological, lexical, and syntactic. In the poetic text of folklore, the category of repetition is particularly active. In this regard, some researchers consider repetition to be the leading category of folklore. Folklore text also includes coherence, a formal and structural category of belonging, a meaningful category of modality, integrativity, and a meaningful conceptual and informational category. Note that the category of repetition is implemented by a modality, which is one of the meaningful categories, expresses various shades and participates in the implementation of such textual categories as ending and integration.

The phonetic-stylistic categories also include the category of symmetry, which is characteristic of the sound system. Although symmetry does not belong to the categories of regularity of language, it plays a fundamental role in the construction of speech, in a more accurate and understandable expression of thought. Note that this feature of language is directly related to natural phenomena; thus, symmetry in nature is manifested in poetry, and in this regard in language through rhythm, and the poetic function of language is based precisely on its communicative function. Symmetry is a speech phenomenon that focuses on sounds at the word level and the parallel use of syntagmas at the sentence level. This fact serves not only to express an emotional attitude, but is also one of the main factors in interesting and attractive speech construction.

Paronymy is also included in phonetic and stylistic categories. Paronymy, presented as a lexico-semantic category, has been studied in our linguistics to some extent only at the lexical level. For paronyms that perform various stylistic functions in fiction, the initial condition for the emergence of these functions is the differentiation of sounds in different conditions. Here, too, the stylistic goal is realized by phonetic means. Baudouin de Courtenay, distinguishing between linguistic and linguistic categories, notes that "linguistic categories are, in fact, categories of linguistics, but they are based on the linguistic sensitivity of the people" [11, p. 60]. Linguistic sensitivity is, of course, the purposeful use of linguistic material, in which pronunciation plays a key role.

Phonetic and stylistic means.

Stylistics distinguishes between phonetic-stylistic categories and phonetic-stylistic means of expression. Although a categorical approach to the issue reveals these differences, it would be wrong to draw a serious line between them; these linguistic phenomena are interrelated and interdependent. Phonetic and stylistic categories are realized precisely through phonetic and stylistic means. If phonetic-stylistic categories manifest themselves as a regular model in the "language-speech" dichotomy, then phonetic-stylistic means of expression in practice act as speech material, manifesting this in speech fragments. I.B. Golub refers to the phonetic and stylistic means of expression as the harmony of vowels and consonants, anaphora and epiphora, as well as consonant sounds, sound images, the emotional function of the sound image, verbal stress, rhythm, rhyme and length of the word [13, p. 162].

I.V. Arnold includes among the phonetic and stylistic means of expression of the author repetition, rhyme, rhythm, meter, alliteration, anaphora, epiphora, etc. [4, p.208].

It should be noted that phonetic and stylistic tools are numerous and diverse; their detailed and comprehensive study is organically linked not only with stylistic research, but also with other areas of linguistics, in particular, with such important areas as experimental phonetics, literary criticism, public speaking and stage language, and even with serious research in areas of literary criticism.

Phonetic and stylistic means include pronunciation harmony, the sound composition of the language,

the arrangement of vowels and consonants, and special phonetic and stylistic means - stress, punctuation, tone, intonation, etc. One of the phonetic and stylistic means of expression is alliteration. The formation of alliteration in any language is associated with certain linguistic patterns. Since alliteration is more often manifested in poetry, researchers note that its origin is related to syntactic parallelism [12, pp. 23-42]. In poetry, harmony, versification, equality, etc. they come from repetition and syntactic parallelism. Grammatical rhymes also arose from syntactic parallelism. As the rhyme developed and improved, alliteration weakened. V.M. Zhirmunsky explains the origin of alliteration in the poetry of the Turkic peoples as a relic of verbal repetition, noting that it was created, in particular, in epics to create "stylistic expressiveness, emotional excitement", and analyzes it based on the material of ancient Turkic epics [15, p. 148]. The author comes to the conclusion that the alliteration characteristic of the Turkic and Mongolian languages, unlike the Germanic languages, is characterized by a free character [14, p. 31].

In conclusion, we note that the stylistic possibilities of phonetics should be understood as using the sound system of a language, its various shades, in their specific place and making the most of it. It is difficult to achieve this goal by memorizing the phonetic rules of a language. Mastering phonetic norms and pronunciation rules in connection with the internal potential of the language, its harmony and melody will provide every native speaker with the opportunity to make full use of phonetic phenomena and laws, as well as phonetic stylistics.

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